

1 **Rab32 activation in ulcerative colitis.**

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8 Citations

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10 1. Alto, N.M., Soderling, J. and Scott, J.D., 2002. Rab32 is an A-kinase anchoring protein and
11 participates in mitochondrial dynamics. *The Journal of cell biology*, 158(4), pp.659-668.

12 2. Wu, Z., Que, H., Li, C., Yan, L., Wang, S. and Rong, Y., 2024. Rab32 family proteins regulate
13 autophagosomal components recycling. *Journal of Cell Biology*, 223(3), p.e202306040.
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